

Virtual Environment Security Baseline Recommendations

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2013 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20130221> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

When I started virtualizing production environment in 2002/2003 many people didn't trust the technology and (to be honest) they didn't understand the technology either. So I had to make big efforts in explaining the advantages of a virtual environment and the best of all arguments was to show them how it worked. Well, I guess I don't have to explain it here anymore.

Still, when it comes to security, there are some more concerns providing a virtual environment. Let's take a view on the following picture:

Figure: Structure of a Virtual Environment

As we can see virtualization is adding a new layer that is susceptible to a new way of attacks and exploitation (after all it's more software code and we all know what it means...) and we need to be aware of it and take the needed precautions as we always should do. This discussion becomes more important when it comes to high risk environments like in a DMZ.

3. Requirements for Virtual Environments

I'm not going to into the details of the security design of a virtual environment as it really depends on the goals you need to achieve.

Also I'm not talking about the security requirements of the virtual systems OS, this is out of scope, we'll only talk about the underlying virtual environment. Although a

secured operating system is a prerequisite in our case, there are plenty of guidelines on how to achieve this.

What I like to point here are the recommended security requirements for a virtual infrastructure architecture as schematic represented in the following picture:

Figure: Security Requirements

We need to take particular care on the new administration environment and on the virtual network layer. As already suggested in the picture one recommendation is clear:

use an isolated administration environment

Managing several machines from a central site with special administration paths, makes the administration environment a clear target for attacks – Why should I attack several different systems when I can get it all at once? Therefore this is probably the best point to start in securing your environment. Make sure you also:

- define a controlled access to the administration environment and
- use a strong authentication where possible

Now let's take a look at the virtual environments new attack areas as shown in the following picture:

Figure: New Attack Areas

Area	Components	Attack
1	VMtools (Client management API)	VM jumping, guest hopping or Hypervisor DoS Attacks
2	VM management (Host management API)	Hypervisor DoS
3	Hypervisor (Virtual Machine Monitor)	Hypervisor escape, Management privilege escalation
4	VM management infrastructure	Management tools unauthorized access, privilege escalation & DoS

Attack areas 1 to 3 are not so common, but the attacks on the administration infrastructure are well known and use the already known paths. This leads to the next recommendation:

keep your virtual environment up to date (including the management infrastructure)

It is crucial to keep those environment patched and if not possible: Implement workarounds (e.g. strict configuration settings) to lower the risk to an acceptable level.

4. Requirements for DMZ Virtual Environments

Particular attention on security requirement is needed in the DMZ (or higher risk) environments where following recommendation are a must:

- **Security Domains:** Do not share same host & network resources for different security domains.
- **Secure Consolidated Logging:** Log collection, consolidation, correlation, alerting & reporting (SIEM).
- **Malware Detection:** Like Intrusion Detection/Prevention.
- **Vulnerability Management:** Vulnerability scanning & reporting on network and system layer.
- **Network Monitoring:** NMS, Business View, KPI monitoring.
- **Virtual Infrastructure Hardening:** Baseline for Hypervisor, VM & Administration Infrastructure.

Of course those requirements make sense in every ICT environment, not only in the virtual ones.

5. Recommended VMware Baseline for DMZ

Now to bring some practical knowledge I'll publish a VMware baseline excerpt that would make sense in our virtualized DMZ environment.

Hypervisor		
Parameter	Description	Value
VirtualCenter.VimPasswordExpirationInDays	Ensure that vpxuser auto-password change meets policy	90 days
Configure the ESXi host firewall to restrict access to services running on the host	–	site specific
Configure NTP time synchronization	/etc/ntp.conf	site specific
Ensure proper SNMP configuration	/etc/vmware/snmp.xml	site specific
Do not use default self-signed certificates for ESXi communication	–	–
Disable DCUI to prevent local administrative control	–	stopped
Disable ESXi Shell unless needed for diagnostics or troubleshooting	–	stopped
Disable SSH	–	stopped
Enable lockdown mode to restrict remote access	–	enabled
Verify no unauthorized kernel modules are loaded on the host	–	–
Configure persistent logging for all ESXi host	Syslog.global.logDir	log directory
Configure remote logging for ESXi hosts	Syslog.global.logHost	syslog-server
Zero out VMDK files prior to deletion	–	–
Virtual Machines (VMtools)		
Parameter	Description	Value
Generic	For directly accessed VM systems like DNS, SMTP & WEB server don't install VMtools at all.	–
vmci0.unrestricted	Disable VM-to-VM communication through VMCI	false
RemoteDisplay.maxConnections	Limit sharing of console connections	2
floppyX.present	Disconnect unauthorized devices	false
ideX:Y.present	Disconnect unauthorized devices	false
parallelX.present	Disconnect unauthorized devices	false

serialX.present	Disconnect unauthorized devices	false
usb.present	Disconnect unauthorized devices	false
isolation.device.connectable.disable	Prevent unauthorized removal, connection and modification of devices.	true
isolation.device.edit.disable	Prevent unauthorized removal, connection and modification of devices.	true
isolation.tools.copy.disable	Explicitly disable copy/paste operations	true
isolation.tools.dnd.disable	Explicitly disable copy/paste operations	true
isolation.tools.setGUIOptions.enable	Explicitly disable copy/paste operations	false
isolation.tools.paste.disable	Explicitly disable copy/paste operations	true
isolation.tools.ghi.autologon.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.bios.bbs.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.getCreds.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.ghi.launchnhmenu.change	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.memSchedFakeSampleStats.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.ghi.protocolhandler.info.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.ghi.hostshellAction.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.unity.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.unityInterlockOperation.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.unity.taskbar.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.unityActive.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.unity.windowContents.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.unity.push.update.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.vmxDNVersionGet.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.guestDNVersionSet.disable	Disable certain unexposed features	true
isolation.tools.autoInstall.disable	Disable tools auto install	true
isolation.tools.vixMessage.disable	Disable VIX messages from the VM	true

Virtual Network		
Parameter	Description	Value
isolate-mgt-network-vlan	Ensure that vSphere management traffic is on a restricted network	–
isolate-storage-network-vlan	Ensure that IP-based storage traffic is isolated	–
isolate-vmotion-network-vlan	Ensure that vMotion traffic is isolated	–
no-unused-dvports	Ensure that there are no unused ports on a distributed virtual port group	–
reject-forged-transmit-dvportgroup	Ensure that the <i>Forged Transmits</i> policy is set to reject.	reject
mac-change-dvportgroup	Ensure that the <i>MAC Address Change</i> policy is set to reject	reject
promiscuous-mode-dvportgroup	Ensure that the <i>Promiscuous Mode</i> policy is set to reject	reject
no-native-vlan-1	Ensure that port groups are not configured to the value of the native VLAN	–
no-reserved-vlans	Ensure that port groups are not configured to VLAN values reserved by upstream physical switches	–
no-vgt-vlan-4095	Ensure that port groups are not configured to VLAN 4095 except for Virtual Guest Tagging (VGT)	–
verify-vlan-id	Ensure that all virtual switch VLAN's are fully documented and have all required and only required VLANs	–
vswitch-forged-transmit	Ensure that the <i>Forged Transmits</i> policy is set to reject	reject
vswitch-mac-changes	Ensure that the <i>MAC Address Change</i> policy is set to reject	reject
vswitch-promiscuous-mode	Ensure that the <i>Promiscuous Mode</i> policy is set to reject	reject

Applying to those recommendation and remembering that security is a process and every control should be monitored and verified, you should have no bigger risk in providing a virtualized DMZ environment.

6. References

- *VMware Hardening Guides* [1]

7. External Links

[1] <http://www.vmware.com/support/support-resources/hardening-guides.html>